

Academic Achievement and Academic Fraudulent Behavior: Effects of Campus Culture, Information Technology Implementation, and Academic Achievement

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 13 July 2023</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Slamet Slamet</p>	<p>Academic fraud is an act committed by students to get maximum results by committing bad and prohibited acts such as cheating, discussing with friends during exams or other ways. The problems formulated in this study are: 1) does campus culture influence fraudulent academic behavior?; Does the use of information technology influence academic fraud behavior?; and 3) does academic achievement influence academic fraud behavior? This type of quantitative research is an ex post facto model with 118 students at Ivet University Semarang as subjects. Data collection techniques used documentation and questionnaires with instruments that met the requirements of validity and reliability. The data analysis technique was used with the help of SPSS data processing, with the results that: 1) based on descriptive statistical analysis, the academic fraud variable was high, while campus culture was relatively high, while the use of information technology was included in the high criteria and the academic achievement score was relatively high; 2) based on hypothesis testing only campus culture variables have a positive and significant effect on academic cheating, while the variables of information technology use and academic achievement are found to have no significant effect on academic cheating.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: campus culture, information technology, achievement, and academic fraudulent.</p>	

I. INTRODUCTION

In the implementation of education, the campus has a function as a capacity developer and the formation of noble national character and civilization in the context of educating the nation's life, besides aiming to develop student potential. The campus explains the way of human life in its environment. In campus cultural studies, adjusting the human condition from a cultural perspective is necessary to see and recognize human intricacies. Students carry out information exchange and academic and social activities to achieve the goals that motivate each student. History has recorded that the long journey of the Indonesian nation cannot be separated from the participation of students. It is expressly stated that campus culture is a scientific study that studies culture, behavior, traditions, values, and interactions, which are considered necessary in the dynamics of the campus world or the surrounding environment related to the campus [1].

Education is the process of teaching, training or researching knowledge, skills and habits passed down from generation to generation, so life in a campus atmosphere becomes a culture [2]. Transformation into changes in intellectual, moral and

social behavior in the individual concerned becomes a culture in campus life [3]. According to this statement, education should free individuals from confinement, intimidation, and exploitation. This is intended so that all the potential within each student develops optimally. Therefore, lecturers have an essential role in the educational process in instilling values and characteristics in students, but in practice, many challenges are encountered, including academic fraud behavior by students.

Academic fraud, or academic cheating/fraud, is an act that uses illegitimate means to gain success in avoiding academic failure [4]. Fraudulent behavior is divided into 3 (three) categories: 1) giving, taking, or receiving certain information; 2) using a prohibited tool; and 3) taking advantage of the weaknesses of people, procedures, and processes to gain an advantage. Furthermore, academic fraud is a behavior that reflects dishonesty intended to obtain the desired academic grades [5]. This condition is because students still have a robust result-oriented view, so that anything will be done, including dishonest behavior as a form of academic cheating.

Academic fraud can have long-term impacts, one of which is the possibility of corruption. Corrupt behavior is unethical behavior carried out anywhere, including in the work environment, and has even become a global problem, which may begin with fraudulent academic behavior. Academic fraud is often carried out in the form of small notes on paper or on a cellphone, copying and pasting from the internet, working with friends during exams and many other forms of fraud [6]. The preventive role of the lecturer is significant so that prohibited actions do not occur.

Based on the explanation above, it can be stated that academic fraud is an act carried out by students to get maximum results by carrying out actions that are not good or prohibited, such as cheating, discussions with friends during exams, collecting group assignments only by entrusting names or other ways. Academic fraud has become commonplace in education circles, including among university students. On the one hand, corruption is an example of the long-term impact of academic fraudulent behavior; on the other hand, education prevents corruption through preventive measures.

Preliminary studies based on previous research and updated news channels are sufficient to form the basis of the phenomenal gap in this research. Academic fraudulent behavior needs to be re-examined regarding its level and relation to the factors that cause it. The main theories that underlie students committing academic fraud in this study are social cognitive theory and achievement goal orientation theory. Social cognitive theory is a new application of social learning theory developed by Albert Bandura in the 70s and 80s. Bandura's main idea is also the development of Miller & Dollard's idea of imitative learning. According to this theory, learning comes not only from self-motivation or human inner strength but also from the surrounding environment [7]. On the other hand, the psychological function is to encourage and strengthen oneself regarding behavior, including continuous reciprocal interactions between behavior and psychological conditions as controllers.

The theory examines how people control their thoughts and actions, namely processes based on setting goals, assessing the possible outcomes of actions, evaluating progress toward achieving goals, and self-regulation of thoughts, emotions, and actions. According to this theory, learning comes from 3 (three) interactions between the environment, internal activities, and individual behavior. This theory includes the development of a self-regulation system as a necessary component and the development of superior performance in every field, including understanding personal toughness, goal setting, self-evaluation, and self-regulated rewards or punishments [8]. Academic fraudulent behavior is one of the students' attitudes toward the inability to control emotions, thoughts, and actions. The role of self-efficacy, in this case, is crucial to prevent and control the behavior of these students.

Another theory that underlies fraudulent academic behavior is the Achievement Goal Orientation Theory. He stated in his writing that A New Direction for Teaching and Learning, with the topic of student orientation towards values and their influence on what is done in learning. It is emphasized that there are two basic student orientations in their studies: grade orientation (work for grades) and learning orientation (work for learning). It is described that the instrument underlying the two basic student orientations is called LOGO (Learning Orientation and Grade Orientation). In achievement goal orientation, individuals with mastery goal orientation seek to master a skill or concept [9]. In general, individuals who have a mastery goal orientation will work hard, survive in the face of adversity and despair, dare to take risks, and try things that have never been done, all to master the task at hand [10].

According to the achievement goal orientation theory, students have two learning goals: performance orientation goals, or learning for results, and learning orientation, or learning to learn (more towards the process). Students with learning objectives focused on processes and strategies can gain abilities and improve skills.

Academic fraudulent behavior is caused by several factors, including learning motivation, student integrity level, and misuse of information technology [11]. In another opinion, students' academic fraudulent behavior is influenced by two factors, namely self-efficacy and school or campus culture [12].

The causes of student academic fraud behavior are caused by diamond fraud (pressure, opportunity, rationality, ability) and smartphone use [13]. Academic fraudulent behavior is caused by two factors: misuse of information technology and student integrity [14]. It was also found that academic fraud were self-efficacy, the learning environment, and learning discipline [15]. Based on previous research, three variables had a strong possibility of causing academic fraud behavior: the campus environment as a form of culture, the use of information technology, and academic achievement.

Previous research can also be used as a research gap related to the influence of campus culture, technology use, and academic achievement on fraudulent academic behavior. The research gap referred to is the variation in the results of the influence of academic fraud behavior on the three variables. The results of research on campus culture that influence academic fraudulent are also presented [15]; [16], but the results of other studies found no effect [17]; [13].

Related to the use of information technology on academic fraud behavior [11], it was found that the use of information technology influenced academic fraud behavior [13]. It was also found that information technology did not affect academic fraud [18]. The third independent variable, academic achievement, influenced academic fraud [19]. At the same time, academic achievement does not affect academic cheating. Previous research with different results is

an exciting research gap to re-examine the results of influence [1].

In line with the description above, fraudulent academic behavior can occur at all levels of education, including at Ivet University Semarang, which has 5 (five) faculties and 25 study programs. Thus, the aims of this study are: 1) to analyze the influence of campus culture on fraudulent academic behavior; 2) to analyze the influence of the use of information technology on academic fraud behavior; and 3) to analyze the effect of academic achievement on academic fraud behavior.

II. METHODOLOGY

This type of research is quantitative because it tests the hypothesis using statistical test tools and figures with statistical data processing, starting from data collection, interpretation, and presentation [20]. The research design belongs to the explanatory type because research seeks to explain causal relationships between variables through hypothesis testing [21].

Based on the causal relationship model, this research uses a quantitative approach with a non-experimental design because it does not treat the subject specifically but examines the facts that have happened and been experienced by the subject. Therefore, the manipulation of variables is not carried out but only explores the facts of events that occur through the questionnaire instrument. Conditions mean that research is conducted after differences in the independent variables occur due to the natural development of events, called ex post facto research (after the fact). The research design was used through hypothesis testing (hypothesis testing study), namely the practice of testing the influence of campus culture, information technology, and academic achievement on academic cheating.

The research subjects were all former students. The Faculty of Education has 118 people, while the data collection tools used documentation and questionnaires. Before the questionnaire instrument was used to collect data, validity and reliability tests were carried out, and all instruments were declared valid and reliable. In contrast, the data analysis technique used multiple regression with the help of the SPSS program.

III. DISCUSSIONS

Research on the effect of the three independent variables (X1, X2, and X2) on the dependent variable was carried out using SPSS data with the results shown as in the following table.

Table Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	26.682	5.850		4.561	.000
X1	.519	.069	.598	7.515	.000
X2	.033	.068	.039	.488	.627
X3	-.097	.060	-.117	-1.608	.111

a. Dependent Variable: Y.

Information:

X1 = Campus culture;

X2 = Information and technology use;

X3 = Academic achievement; and

Y = Academic fraudulent behaviour.

Based on the problems raised and solved through the worktable above, the following discussion can be carried out.

A. The Influence of Campus Culture on Academic Fraudent

Based on hypothesis testing, the results show that campus culture positively and significantly affects fraudulent academic behavior. This can be seen from the unstandardized coefficient beta value of 0.519 and a significance of 0.000. The significance value is below the significance level of 0.05, meaning H1 is accepted. This condition means that fraudulent academic behavior will increase if students have strong interactions with campus culture. Conversely, fraudulent academic behavior decreases if students interact less with campus culture.

Based on the descriptive statistical analysis test results, the campus culture variable has an average value of 42.08 with a minimum value of 29 and a maximum value of 50. The descriptive statistical analysis results show the level of agreement, which means that the subject has a strong interaction with campus culture. In addition, the descriptive statistical analysis results indicate that Ivet University is an educational institution that has provided a campus culture that is comfortable and representative as well as conducive and supports the implementation of the learning process. Such campus cultural conditions make students accustomed to communicating and interacting with elements of the campus environment, such as lecturers, students, campus rules, and learning media. Intense interaction causes students to find loopholes or opportunities to do something, one of which is academic fraud behavior. The campus culture influences the occurrence of academic fraud behavior.

Social cognitive theory has several assumptions about learning and behavioral practice. This assumption discusses the mutual interaction between humans, behavior, and the environment; learning through practice and observation; the difference between learning and practice; and self-regulation. Human behavior can interact in a three-sided framework or reciprocal interactions between behavior, environmental or cultural variables, and personal factors such as cognition [22]. The campus as a place of learning has a major influence on student self-development, which is obtained from experience on campus, both academic and non-academic activities. Humans, behavior, environment, and culture are a unity that cannot be separated because they are interrelated. This means that student behavior, namely academic cheating, cannot be separated from the surrounding environment in the form of campus culture.

The results of the study state that campus culture influences fraudulent academic behavior. These results are in line with the results of previous studies [15]; [17]. Almost all student academic activities are carried out on campus, so campus culture influences actions, including fraudulent academic behavior. Friends' invitations can drive this behavior, as lecturers who cannot convey material, facilities that are not supportive, and other factors. However, these results are not in line with previous research, which found no effect [13]; [17].

B. Impacts of Information Technology Use Toward Academic Fraudulence

Based on hypothesis testing, the results show that using information technology has no significant effect on academic fraud behavior. This can be seen from the unstandardized coefficient beta value of 0.033 and a significance of 0.627. The significance value is above the significance level of 0.05, meaning H2 is rejected. This means that if students have a high or low level of ability to use information technology, then the level of academic fraud will remain or stagnate. This means that academic fraud has nothing to do with the intensity of the use of information technology.

Based on the descriptive statistical analysis test results, the information technology usage variable has an average value of 41.18 with a minimum value of 26 and a maximum value of 50. The descriptive statistical analysis results show that the level of information technology is strongly agreed upon, which means that the subject has a high and good level of information technology use. In addition, the descriptive statistical analysis results indicate that Universitas Ivet, as an educational institution, has provided good information technology facilities such as computers and network access. In online learning during a pandemic, for example, information technology's role is vital. All academic activities on campus are carried out online using application facilities such as Zoom, Google Meet, WhatsApp, Telegram, Instagram, and other information applications. Therefore, the use of information

technology must be distinct from student activities. Learning technology facilities have been equipped with an integrated system and accompanied by regular campus supervision so that there is no loophole for students to commit academic fraud.

Achievement goal orientation theory is a general theory of motivation that refers to the fact that the types of goals people work for tremendously impact how a goal is pursued. This theory confirms that there are two types of students in learning: grade orientation (work for grades) and learning orientation (work to learn). Students with the grade orientation type have more opportunities to commit academic fraud than those with the learning orientation type [22]. Most students at Ivet Semarang University have a learning orientation that prioritizes knowledge and insight gained as a goal, but students still have the motivation to pursue grades. Such student characteristics make it easier for lecturers to supervise and learn because students are usually more enthusiastic about participating in learning and staying away from deviant behavior, such as fraudulent academic behavior. Therefore, the use of information technology does not affect fraudulent academic behavior.

The study's results stated that the use of information technology had no effect on academic fraud behavior and followed the results of previous studies [18]. Information technology is important in learning activities, especially in the 2013 curriculum, updated with the Merdeka Belajar Kampus Medeka Curriculum (MBKM). This curriculum prioritizes students rather than the role of the lecturer (student center) in finding learning references. Technology can be in the form of smartphones, computers, or laptops. The role of the lecturer is more passive than in previous periods, so it is more flexible in supervising the student learning process. Extra supervision can monitor the use of information technology in accordance with the objectives so that acts of academic fraud can be minimized. However, these results differ from previous results, which show that the use of information technology has a significant effect on academic fraud behavior [11]; [14].

C. The Effect of Academic Achievement on Academic Fraudulent

Based on hypothesis testing, it appears that academic achievement has no significant effect on fraudulent academic behavior. This can be seen from the unstandardized coefficient beta value of 0.097 and a significance level of 0.111. The significance value is above the significance level of 0.05, which means that H3 is rejected. If students have high or low academic achievement scores, academic fraud behavior will remain or stagnate. This means academic fraud does not affect students' academic achievement levels.

Based on the descriptive statistical analysis test results, the academic achievement variable has an average value of 81.65, with a minimum score of 75 and a maximum score of 95. The results of the descriptive statistical analysis show the academic

achievement of Ivet Semarang University students as seen from the General Basic Courses (Pancasila Education, Education Religion, Technopreneurship, and Learning Theory) at a good level (B). Academic achievements obtained by students must be distinct from learning elements such as lecturers, students, learning media, and learning models. If the academic achievement is good enough, the learning elements are also going well. Students with high academic achievement will have more pride. In addition, high academic achievement can build a promising paradigm for students from the viewpoint of the surrounding environment. This paradigm is always maintained, one of which is not to commit deviant acts such as academic cheating. Therefore, the level of academic achievement obtained does not influence students to commit academic fraud.

It was argued that mastery goal orientation is a motivational orientation owned by individuals, emphasizing knowledge acquisition and self-improvement. This shows that students who have a high learning orientation will make a persistent effort to master the material and are more motivated to study hard in order to obtain excellent or high academic achievement. The principle of learning in students is fundamental to apply so that the learning orientation is directed [3]. Ivet Semarang University students have a work orientation to study or a learning orientation, so they are very enthusiastic about participating in the learning process. This type of student prioritizes knowledge rather than the results obtained. The learning orientation emphasizes the process rather than the results or outputs that follow later. This orientation causes academic achievement to be quite good; besides, it also makes students minimize or even eliminate deviant behavior such as academic cheating.

The results of the study state that academic achievement does not affect fraudulent academic behavior that has been documented in previous studies [1]. Pure academic achievement results from the hard work of students' learning and is only influenced by learning elements. Learning outcomes give rise to a sense of pride in the students themselves. Students with a learning orientation type try to maintain pride and even increase that pride by not carrying out prohibited actions such as academic cheating. Therefore, academic performance does not affect academic cheating. The results of this study are not in line with previous research, which states that academic achievement affects academic fraudulent [19].

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that: 1) campus culture has a positive and significant effect on academic cheating; 2) the use of information technology has no significant effect on academic cheating; and 3) academic achievement has no significant effect on student academic cheating. Based on the conclusions, it is recommended that

educational institutions continuously improve the creation of an academic atmosphere and a comfortable and pleasant environment to minimize fraudulent academic behavior among students. In addition, there is also a need to increase supervision of the use of information technology to maintain character as a form of personality and increase academic achievement for students. It is suggested that future researchers add or modify the research variables used to be broader in explaining the factors that influence academic fraudulent.

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